

Investigation Of Solar Hybrid System With Thermoelectric Generator

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ABSTRACT

This paper is discussing on the behaviour and performance of Thermoelectric Generator and Solar Cell Panel in a hybrid mode. A Solar Panel of its own can produce an electric energy, but during high temperature condition especially during daylight, the performance of Solar Arrays may drop immediately depending on the surrounding environment. To ensure output power electric is stay at its optimum, Thermoelectric Generator is used to support the output energy supply, and also to boost electric power. The combination of this harvesting technique with the use of Step-up Converter with MPPT(maximum power point tracking) can be used to charge small mobile devices like smartphones. The voltage output was observed by using DAQ-card reader and connected to MATLAB to obtain the voltage reading. The performance of Thermal Electric Generator also observed by using Picolog Data Logger to obtains the temperature reading for cold side and hot side of Thermal Electric Generator. The result show the improvement of voltage output for Solar Panel. This improvement can be used to meet voltage drop during high temperature condition. The Step-up Converter also provide the enough voltage need for charging the small device by using small output Solar Panel but lack in current need.

Keywords: (Hybrid system; Thermoelectric Generator; Solar Panel; Step-up Converter; Maximum Power Point Tracking)

ABSTRAK

Kertas ini membincangkan tentang tingkah laku dan prestasi Penjana Termoelektrik dan juga Panel Solar dalam keadaan hibrid. Secara amnya, Panel Solar sendiri sudah mampu untuk menjana tenaga elektrik, namun dalam keadaan suhu yang tinggi, terutamanya ketika waktu tengah hari, prestasi Panel Solar akan menurun disebabkan keadaan persekitaran yang panas mempengaruhi suhu permukaan Panel Solar. Untuk memastikan kuasa elektrik keluaran sentiasa berada dalam keadaan optimum, Penjana Termoelektrik digunakan untuk menampung tenaga keluaran yang menurun dan juga meningkatkan kuasa elektrik yang dijana. Teknik gabungan untuk penuaian tenaga ini dengan Penukar Langkah-naik dengan PTKM (penjejak titik kuasa maksimum) boleh dimanfaatkan untuk mengecas peranti mudah alih seperti telefon pintar. Voltan keluaran diperhatikan dengan menggunakan pembaca DAQ-card dan disambungkan kepada perisian MATLAB untuk mendapatkan bacaan voltan. Prestasi bagi Penjana Termoelektrik turut diperhatikan dengan menggunakan Picolog Data Logger untuk mendapatkan bacaan suhu untuk sisi sejuk dan sisi panas Penjana Termoelektrik. Keputusan menunjukkan peningkatan voltan keluaran untuk Panel Solar. Ianya boleh digunakan untuk memenuhi kejatuhan voltan semasa keadaan suhu tinggi. Penukar Langkah-naik juga menyediakan keperluan voltan yang cukup untuk mengecas peranti kecil dengan menggunakan Panel Solar berkapasiti rendah tetapi mempunyai kekurangan dari segi arus elektrik yang dijana.

Kata Kunci: (Sistem Hibrid; Penjana Termoelektrik; Solar Panel; Penukar Langkah-naik; Penjejak Titik Kuasa Maksimum).

INTRODUCTION

Demand for electricity consumption is growing every year resulting in the production of electrical energy annually always increasing. However, the main methods for conventional electricity generation is using thermal power plants where coal and oil are also used as fuel for the production of water vapour to drive a generator. The use of this fuel is continuously regardless of the point of electricity generation or transportation cause fuel reserves is dwindling even be exhausted at some point. This sparked concern to all parties because electricity is a necessity in human life. Hence the effort expanded in search of an alternative method to replace the method of generating electricity conventional that may not be relevant again in the future if fuel reserves began to run out. Among the successful method developed by scientists at the moment is a thermoelectric generator and solar energy which is renewable energy. Method of generating electricity from sunlight is very widely grown because of this energy source belong to the category of renewable energy as well as an ongoing source (S. Maninder et al. 2016). Power generation from solar is divided into two types, namely Photovoltaic and also the Thermal. Photovoltaic cell converts directly convert sunlight to electricity while thermal technology trap the heat produced by solar energy is converted to mechanical energy before converted to electricity. It is also known as the concentration of solar energy. The energy generated is free and users just need to install the pieces-solar pieces at a certain place to allow sunlight absorbed. While Thermoelectric Generator in turn took the initiative from the phenomenon, whose seeback effects when two electrical conductors or half different conductor placed together at different temperatures, it would produce an electric potential. However, the solar panels have a very low level of efficiency compared with the energy the Sun received per day. What causes the occurrence of loss of energy during the conversion of this energy is the energy of the Sun is not a hundred-percent converted to electricity, but converted to other forms, especially in the form of heat.

SOLAR PANEL

Solar panels become more famous tools today as alternative for power substitution harvesting technique to generate electricity in future. There are many scale of Solar Panels that can be used to generate electrical power. A single with small panel can be used in small application as well to charging or used directly power supply. These small scale of Panel Solar can be used for charging small device like cell Phone including smartphone. In the others hand, a large scale of panels can be used together to generate electricity in National Grid. In real situation actually Photovoltaic cell did not have constantly output voltage, the voltage actually have behavior like this

FIGURE 1. Output power from Solar Panel.

THERMOELECTRIC GENERATOR(TEG)

Thermoelectric materials had their first decisive long-term test with the start of intensive deep-space research. During the Apollo mission, thermoelectric materials were responsible for the power supply, and currently, radioisotope thermoelectric generators (RTGs) are the power supplies (350 W) used in deep-space missions beyond Mars (J. T. Jarman et al. 2013). Thermoelectric Generator is a technique used to generate the electric energy from the Seebeck effect phenomena. This phenomena occurs when there are two different temperature in two metal, produce emf in the tip between the metal. In early stage of this theory, it was apply in making thermometer, then the future research show that the Seebeck effect actually can be used to generate electricity. A Thermoelectric Generator can produce electrical from the heat across the temperature gradient. Effect from this action causes the carrier charge in material in substances drive to tip of the cold side. Voltage (v) produce is propotional to the temperature different (ΔT) through Seebeck constant, α , ($V = \alpha \Delta T$), (Jeffrey Snyder 2008).

$$zT = \frac{\alpha^2 T}{\rho \kappa}$$

MAXIMUM POWER POINT TRACKING (MPPT)

In the real condition, output power from the solar is actually varies by time, there are no constant output coming from Photovoltaic cell. This happen due to temperature varience and also the sun radiation. The MPPT module work with detecting the maximum power output from the Solar Panel and trying to maintain the power (Cullen R. A. 2000). The type of application can have a significant impact on the selection of MPPT algorithm (S. E. Baaba et al. 2014). Figure 2 below show that conventional charger controller vs Solar boost MPPT controller.

FIGURE 2. Conventional charger controller vs Solar boost MPPT controller.

STEP-UP CONVERTER

Step-up converter or DC-DC converter is a device that use to boost the input voltage magnitude without using Transformer. The basic circuit of this converter is like below,

FIGURE 3. Basic circuit of this converter

This Boost converter operate in two mode,during the switch is closing and the switch is opening.

1.Switch opening

During this time inductor is charging by the DC input voltage.

2.Switch closing

During this time inductor is discharging to the load together with the input DC voltage.This operation give improvement to the output voltage to the load.

METHODOLGY

SYSTEM WITHOUT LOAD

FIGURE 5. Basic of hybrid system without Step-up

In this experiment,the source of Halogen lamp was used as souce of light and heat. The circuit for experiment was built based on two system.The first system is testing the voltage output without the load and the others system is testing the output with the load.In this experiment,the smartphone with 2600 mAh battery capacity is used as load for charging mode.The experiment performing step by step starting with the stand alone system using Solar Panel only continuing with Thermoelectric Generator(TEG).To ensure the output power always in stable,we need some additional device like DC-DC Converter to makesure the output power always in optimum value.

STAND ALONE SYSTEM

SOLAR PANEL

The stand alone system is system that built with only one source of power input.

FIGURE 6. Direct observation from Panel Solar.

In this experiment, a stand alone system was testing without load. The result is testing on the behavior of Solar Panel on the temperature effect.

THERMOELECTRIC GENERATOR

The stand alone system by Thermoelectric Generator is used the Hot Plate device as source of heat.

FIGURE 7. Block diagram for Thermoelectric Generator(TEG).

The effect on temperature gradient is observed by referring to hot side and cold side temperature.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

STAND ALONE SYSTEM

FIGURE 8. Output from Panel Solar in first 30 minutes.

FIGURE 9. Output from Panel Solar after 30 minutes.

In this experiment, it shows that the voltage from solar panel is drop from 2v to 1.9v due the heat produce by the Halogen lamp. The temperature of Solar Panel surface cause the drop in voltage output.

THERMOELECTRIC GENERATOR (TEG).

Table 1 shows the behavior of Thermoelectric generator in single mode and Table 2 shows behaviour for six TEG in series Series.

TABLE 1. Voltage output from a single TEG.

HOT PLATE TEMPERATURE (°C)	COLD SIDE TEMPERATURE(°C)	HOT SIDE TEMPERATURE(°C)	TEMPERATURE DIFFERENT ΔT (°C)	OUTPUT VOLTAGE (V)
40	42.6	26.5	16.1	0.076
50	51.8	28.0	23.8	0.142

TABLE 2. Voltage output from a six TEG in series.

TIME (S)	COLD SIDE TEMPERATURE(°C)	HOT SIDE TEMPERATURE(°C)	TEMPERATURE DIFFERENT ΔT (°C)	OUTPUT VOLTAGE (V)
60	42.3	25.2	17.1	0.156
120	43.7	25.6	18.1	0.235
180	45.8	26.5	19.3	0.242

From the experiment,we can see that gradient of temperature between cold side and hot side for thermoelectric generator give an important role in output voltage.In increasing different temperature give more voltage output for Thermoelectric Generator (TEG).

HYBRID MODE FOR SOLAR PANEL AND TEG.

FIGURE 10. Hybrid system without Step-up Converter.

Based on figure 10, the result show that the maximum voltage output coming from TEG and Solar Panel not exceed 2.5v. In this situation, the voltage output cannot achieve the requirement voltage for charging small electronic device. But the hybrid between TEG and Solar Panel shows some of increment. In this case, the magnitude of voltage supply by TEG to Solar system is almost same as its loss during high temperature.

FIGURE 11. Hybrid system using Step-up Converter with MPPT.

The result in figure 11, shows the voltage output for system with using Step-up Converter with MPPT. The voltage output increase to 5.9 v. In this condition, the voltage can be apply to load.

SYSTEM WITH LOAD

This system is observation on behavior of voltage of hybrid system on load. This experiment is apply on Smartphone with power charging requirement is 5v and 1 Amp.

FIGURE 12. Hybrid system using Step-up Converter with MPPT on load.

The result in Figure 12 shows that the hybrid system have an ability to charge the load, but in a slow rate. There are ripple voltage when load was apply. This happen due to insufficient power supply from the system to load.

CONCLUSION

The system that have been built shows the comparison between the voltage output for stand alone system and the hybrid system. The TEG vottage can be used to support the losses of voltage by Solar Panel during high temperature condition. On the other hand, by using DC-DC Converter also improve that, the low power of small Solar Panel can be used on the load with high demand of voltage supply. This small experiment actually can be improved by making the small and easy device to harvest energy from sun in hard condition live like in desert and in the jungle. In the field of renewable energy, self-provided research in developing countries is barely present (N. Gentile et al. 2013), so it can be imply on all of these country on developing renewable energy. This system also has the possibility of usability on a larger scale as technique to supply energy on the National Grid (Cédric Philibert et al. 2011).

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